

Reactions of some platinum(II) complexes – hydrolysis, ring opening and substitution[†]

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This review describes the kinetics of hydrolysis and substitution reactions of platinum(II) complexes studied recently. In some of the above reactions reported from our laboratory, a ring opening phenomenon of the parent chelates has been observed. The preference for sulphur atom in bonding in the case of sulfur containing ligands is noteworthy.

The nobility of platinum group metals depends on their large number of valence d-electrons which are available for tight cohesive bonding. It is the same valence shell d-electrons that provide a series of orbitals of a range of energies and symmetries capable of matching and hence bonding with those of a range of simple substrates such as hydrogen, carbon monoxide, olefins and acetylenes. Thus the origin of nobility and catalytic ability of these metals are not dissimilar¹. At the present time, several important processes involving platinum group-catalysed reactions with synthesis gas components are commercially viable ventures². The organometallic chemistry of palladium and platinum and the use of complexes of these metals in homogeneous catalysis have developed tremendously since the early 1970's. This encompasses : (a) the synthesis and properties of organometallic and related complexes of palladium, platinum, rhodium, osmium etc., (b) mechanistic studies of the organo-palladium and -platinum compounds, e.g., addition and elimination reactions, insertions, substitutions and isomerisations, (c) uses of platinum metal complexes in homogeneous catalysis, ranging from mechanistic studies to models of metal surfaces to applications in organic synthesis.

Rosenberg's discovery of the anticancer action of *cis*-dichlorodiammineplatinum(II), cisplatin, in the 1960's^{3–5} precipitated a widespread research for related complexes with similar or better activity. As a consequence, the motivation of today's research on platinum metal chemistry has been directed greatly towards : (a) designing model anticancer compounds, (b) selective tracing of the parts of a protein molecule so as to get an insight about its conformation near the bonding site, (c) solution studies related to the kinetics of interaction of amino acids, peptides, nucleobases, nucleosides etc.

General aspects of substitution reactions of platinum(II) and palladium(II) complexes

The substitution reactions of platinum(II) and palla-

dium(II) complexes have been reviewed in the past^{6,7}. Some recent literatures concerning the kinetics, thermodynamic and structural features are presented in Table 1 with the titles.

Table 1. Recent reviews on platinum(II) and palladium(II) complexes

Title	Ref.
The relevance of hydrogen bonding in the mechanism of action of platinum antitumor compounds	8
Complex compounds of platinum(II) and (IV) with aminoacids, peptides and their derivatives	9
Recollections of early studies on platinum(II) complexes related to Chatt's contributions to coordination chemistry	10
The influence of structure on the activity and toxicity of Pt anticancer drugs	11
Donor atom preferences in complexes of platinum and palladium with amino acids and related molecules	12
Palladium(II) complexes of aliphatic polyamine ligands in aqueous solution : thermodynamic and structural features	13
Interaction of nitrogen bases with some platinum(II) and palladium(II) complexes – usual and unusual features	14

Ligand substitution reactions of square-planar platinum(II) complexes occur with retention of configuration. The kinetics of substitution reactions of square-planar complexes (equation 1) follow a two term rate law,

$$\text{rate} = \{k_1 + k_2 [\text{Y}^-]\} [\text{MA}_3\text{X}] \quad (2)$$

where k_1 is a first order rate constant and k_2 , a second order rate constant, and $[\text{Y}^-]$ represents the concentration of the entering ligand. Both routes are thought to involve an associative (A) mechanism. Convincing evidence in favour of a dissociative mechanism involving a platinum(II) 3-coordinated intermediate comes not from classical Werner compounds but from reactions involving organometallic sub-

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strates¹⁵. The kinetics of solvent exchange and displacement by bidentate ligands on *cis*-[Pt(R)₂(L)₂] (R = CH₃ or C₆H₅; L = sulfoxide or thioether) complexes have provided a clearcut example of ligand dissociation as the dominant step in substitution reactions of square-planar complexes^{16,17}.

Some recent reactions of platinum(II) complexes

Hydrolytic reactions and ring opening phenomenon :

The kinetics of hydrolysis of cisplatin has been investigated in detail. It has become evident that hydrolysis takes place before binding to DNA can occur, i.e. the hydrolytic products are believed to be the active antitumor agents¹⁸. The rate of hydrolysis in water has been measured by conductance study¹⁹⁻²³, spectrophotometry²⁴⁻²⁷, HPLC²⁸⁻³¹, Cl⁻ ion titration^{32,33}, Cl⁻ specific electrode^{34,35}, ³⁶Cl⁻ ion exchange^{36,37}, or H⁺ ion titration³⁸. The latter technique can be used because as the reaction progresses, there is a decrease in pH owing to reaction (4),

The rate of loss of the chloro ligand (k_1) from *cis*-[PtCl₂(NH₃)₂] to give an equilibrium *cis*-[PtCl(NH₃)₂], *cis*-[PtCl(NH₃)₂(OH₂)]⁺ and Cl⁻ mixture has been measured spectrophotometrically in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄, 1.0 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄, and 0.1 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ plus 0.9 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ over the range of temperature 28–50°. The effect of [H⁺] and ionic strength in the above range is small. At 25° ($I = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³, HClO₄) the kinetic parameters are $k_1 = 6.3 \times 10^{-5}$ s⁻¹, $E_a = 84.7 \pm 1.9$ kJ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -49 \pm 3$ JK mol⁻¹. Removal of the released Cl⁻ from the equilibrium solution (0.1 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄) by anion exchange chromatography with the resin in the ClO₄⁻ form generates a solution containing about 90% *cis*-[PtCl(NH₃)₂(OH₂)]⁺. It has been shown that the rate of loss of the chloro ligand from *cis*-[PtCl(NH₃)₂(OH₂)]⁺ is slower than the loss of the first chloro ligand from *cis*-[PtCl₂(NH₃)₂], whereas the rate from *cis*-[PtCl(NH₃)₂(OH)] is comparable or greater^{22,38}. Consequently, while *cis*-[PtCl₂(NH₃)₂] certainly solvolyses in water, the nature of the products cannot be predicted and the rate of reaction can only be securely monitored by measuring the rate of loss of the starting material³⁰. The kinetics of the acid hydrolysis of carboplatin, [*cis*-diammine-

(cyclobutane-1,1-dicarboxylato)platinum(II)] (1) has been studied³⁹ over a range of acidities at constant ionic strength ($I = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³) and range of temperature 19.8 – 34.8°. Loss of the substituted malonato ligand occurs in a biphasic manner which involves a ring opening step and a slower step in which loss of the monodentate malonato ligand takes place.

In the presence of chloride, there is a first order dependence⁴⁰ of ring opening on the chloride concentration with $k_{obs} = k_{Cl}[Cl^-]$, where $k_{Cl} = 1.3 \times 10^{-4}$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 80°. The plasma chloride concentration is 0.104 mol dm⁻³ (compared to 0.004 mol dm⁻³ within cells) so that at the plasma chloride concentrations, $k_{obs} = 1.3 \times 10^{-5}$ at 80° ($t_{1/2} = 14.7$ h). At 37° the half-life of the Cl⁻ reaction is likely to be of the order of 250 h. Such a slow reaction is unlikely to be of biological importance and effectively excludes the idea that carboplatin is simply a prodrug for cisplatin.

A recent report⁴¹ on the hydrolysis of the platinum(II) complexes, [Pt(dien)Cl]⁺ and [PtCl(NH₃)₃]⁺ was conducted with an objective to settle over the apparent dispute between observations of a solvent-assisted pathway in chloride substitution reactions on the one hand, and the failure to observe chloride release on the other. With the help of UV spectrophotometry, it has been possible to follow the hydrolysis of both the complexes. The hydrolytic rate constant (k_H) was determined in acidic aqueous solution ($4.2 \leq pH \leq 5$) at 20° as 6.5×10^{-5} s⁻¹ for [Pt(dien)Cl]⁺ and 1.1×10^{-5} s⁻¹ for [PtCl(NH₃)₃]⁺. The extent of hydrolysis is, however, limited by relatively high chloride anation rate constant of $ca. 10^{-1}$ mol⁻¹ dm³ s⁻¹ at 20°. This fast anation step probably prevented the hydrolysis from being detected in some of the earlier investigations. The kinetics of acid hydrolysis of [Pt(glygly)Cl]⁻ (where, glygly denotes glycylglycine) has been studied⁴² over a range of [H⁺] = 0.1–1.0 mol dm⁻³, ionic strength = 1.0 mol dm⁻³ and temperature 25–45°. The reactions are biphasic in nature — the faster acid catalysed step corresponding to the opening of carboxylate ring, and the slower one to the release of chloride ion. The sequence of reactions can be represented as

and the ring-opened species (2) should have the following structure

The faster rate for the ring opening in comparison to that in carboplatin³⁹ may be due to the added influence of ligand geometry or to the favorable entropy factor (more negative in $[\text{Pt}(\text{glygly})\text{Cl}]^-$ complex).

Substitution reactions with N-bases and ring opening phenomenon :

The complexation of platinum(II) and palladium(II) complex ions with different nucleic acid moieties has been described in relation to the antitumor activity of *cis*- $[\text{PtCl}_2(\text{NH}_3)_2]$ and its derivatives. The chemical aspects mainly focused on include the location of the binding sites^{43a-c} of the various nucleobases and the structure^{44a,b} and stability order/constant^{45a,b} of the resulting complex species. The complexation of guanosine 5'-monophosphate with *cis*- $[\text{PtCl}_2(\text{NH}_3)_2]$ or its ethylenediamine analogue is believed to occur via the dichloro complex and the corresponding mono aqua species at pH 6.5 but not via the diaqua species⁴⁶. On the other hand, *cis*- $[\text{PtCl}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+$ reacts about 15 times faster than the dichloro analogue with adenosine at pH 3.0⁴⁷.

The first hydrolytic product of *cis*- $[\text{PtCl}_2(\text{NH}_3)_2]$ has been shown to be the active partner during reaction with inosine in the pH range 3.5–4.0. The kinetic study has been conducted by HPLC technique⁴⁸. The substitution reactions of $[\text{Pt}(\text{dien})\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2+}$ (dien = diethylenetriamine) with inosine (3) and 1-methylinosine (4) in the pH range 4.2–8.4 have been carried out by Arpalahti and Lehtikoinen⁴⁹.

The aqua analogue is the reactive one, and it binds to N(7) of both inosine and 1-methylinosine. On increasing pH >6, an additional coordination through the N(1) occurs but the N(7) is considered to be the kinetically favoured site for binding. However, prolonged reaction of aquated Pt^{II} (dien) with an excess of adenosine at *ca.* 85° in aqueous solution⁵⁰ leads to a substantial increase in the proportion of N(1)-bound species with a consequential decrease of the N(7)-bound isomer. The kinetic behaviour of *trans*- $[\text{PtCl}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+$ towards inosine and 1-methylinosine in the pH range 2.8–8.4 is comparable to that of the monofunctional $[\text{Pt}(\text{dien})\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2+}$ complex⁵¹. The greater *trans*-effect exerted by Cl^- over H_2O seems to be the cause of such behaviour. It is also to be noted that the rate parameters are of the same orders of magnitude, and this possibly originates from the similar *trans*-effect of Cl^- to that of the –NH group in the tridentate dien ligand. The *trans*-effect order, $\text{Cl}^- > \text{NH}_3 \approx \text{ino-N}(7) > \text{H}_2\text{O}$, is reflected in the relative reactivity of *trans*- $[\text{PtCl}_2(\text{NH}_3)_2]$, *trans*- $[\text{PtCl}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+$ and *trans*- $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ towards inosine which follows as 1 : 200 : 10. A recent study relates to the kinetics of forward and reverse reactions of the process,

$$[\text{Pt}(\text{terpy})\text{Cl}]^+ + \text{amine} \leftrightarrow [\text{Pt}(\text{terpy})(\text{amine})]^{2+} + \text{Cl}^-$$

(terpy = 2,2' : 6',2''-terpyridine and amine = NH_3 and several pyridine derivatives having different basicities) in methanol⁵². The specific second order rate constant is correlated to the LFER according to $k_2^f = \alpha pK_a + \text{constant}$ having $\alpha = 0.24$ for the isosteric pyridine, 4-cyanopyridine, methylisonicotinate etc. The reactivity of the above pyridine derivatives is slightly greater than that of NH_3 . This can originate from the small differences in solvation of the ligands and/or to a π -interacting property for the latter bases. In an identical way, the LFER plot for the dependence of reactivity on the basicity of the leaving N-bases leads to $\alpha = -0.53$ for the complexes having the unhindered pyridines, e.g. 3-methylpyridine, 4-methylpyridine and 4-aminopyridine.

The reactions of monoanionic complexes of the type $[\text{Pt}(\text{LCl})_3]^-$ [L = DMSO, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$, PR_3 , $\text{P}(\text{OCH}_3)_3$, $\text{As}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$] with amine and heterocyclic bases have been reported by Tobe *et al.*^{53–57}. In the reaction of $[\text{Pt}(\text{pic})(\text{L})(\text{Y})]^-$ (where Hpic = pyridine-2-carboxylic acid; L = Cl, NO_2 ; Y = Cl) with the Lewis bases, e.g. N_3^- , NCS^- and NO_2^- , analysis of data from detailed kinetic studies⁵⁸ reflect that these are much more reactive than their n_{Pt}^0 values. Addition of OH^- ion does not influence the rate of reaction with azide, and so this anomaly cannot be ascribed to the catalysis by HN_3 which would be suppressed by this treatment or to attack on the carbonyl carbon which the hydroxide could do much more effectively.

Kinetics of the interaction of four azole bases (e.g. imidazole, benzimidazole, pyrazole and triazole) with $[\text{Pt}(\text{dien})\text{Br}]^+$ have been studied in aqueous solution (27°) by conductometric and spectrophotometric methods⁵⁹. The reactions follow normal square-planar substitution having the rate law under pseudo-first order condition, $k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2 [\text{azole base}]$. The aged solution of $[\text{Pt}(\text{dien})\text{Br}]^+$ shows biphasic reaction traces due to formation of the reactive intermediate $[\text{Pt}(\text{dien})\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2+}$ in solution.

The explanation is supported from that of Goswami *et al.*⁴⁶ who have shown that the monoaqua analogue of *cis*- $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ reacts with a faster rate than the dichloro complex. Kinetics of the anation reaction of $[\text{Pt}(\text{dipic}_{\text{tr}})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($\text{dipic}_{\text{tr}} = 2,6$ -pyridinedicarboxylate ion with subscript (tr) denoting its tridentate bonding mode) with *N*-heterocyclic (azole) bases, e.g. imidazole, benzimidazole and pyrazole in DMF medium have been carried out⁶⁰. The study assumes significance in view of the fact that the tridentate dipic ligand transforms to a bidentate (dipic_{bi}) one allowing the entry of the second molecule of the azole base. To verify and compare such a type of anation followed by the entrance of another nucleophile involving the ring opening, kinetic study of these azole bases with $[\text{Pt}(\text{dipic}_{\text{tr}})(\text{azole base})]$ has been further examined. The study emphasises an interesting type of substitution kinetics whereby all the steps have been scrutinized in detail and substantiated by product isolation, IR and NMR spectral analysis.

The above results have prompted us further to continue the reaction⁶¹ with nucleophiles having mono-, bi- and ambidentate nature, i.e. 1-methylimidazole, ethylenediamine and nicotinic acid to look into the extent of steric requirement (hindrance) for such ring opening phenomenon. The platinum(II) substrate chosen is $[\text{Pt}(\text{dipic})\text{Cl}]^-$, where the previous kinetic study of chloride displacement with anionic nucleophiles (e.g., OH^- , I^- , Br^- , SCN^- etc.) has not explored⁶² the important aspect of ring opening. The successive entry of two 1-methylimidazole molecules through initial chloride ion replacement followed by carboxylate ring opening was followed kinetically. This was further verified through intermediate product isolation. Bidentate ethylenediamine ligand gets chelated with the platinum(II) complex through slow chloride replacement and rapid ring opening process. Due to steric reasons, nicotinic acid shows only the chloride substitution reaction. All the reaction products have been isolated and characterised through ^1H NMR spectra.

Substitution reactions with S-containing ligands :

Reaction of chelated complexes of the type $[\text{PtCl}_2(\text{amino}$

acid)] (amino acid = anion of glycine, sarcosine and *N,N*-dimethylglycine) with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) results in the formation of isomeric complexes, *cis*-(*N,S*)- and *trans*-(*N,S*)- $[\text{Pt}(\text{amino acid})(\text{DMSO})\text{Cl}]^{63}$. In equilibrium, the *cis*-isomer is favoured by a factor of 45 for glycine derivative. Lempers and Reedijk⁶⁴ showed that the complex $[\text{Pt}(\text{dien})\text{Cl}]^+$ reacts preferentially with the sulfur atom of *S*-adenosyl-L-homocysteine in acidic aqueous medium (pH <5), while under basic conditions (pH >7), a rearrangement of the ligand takes place and it now coordinates in monodentate fashion through the cysteine amino group. This is in keeping with the observations of Romeo and Cusumano⁶⁵ who suggested earlier that soft-soft Pt-S interaction is reasonably stable when a single DMSO is bound to the Pt(dien) moiety. However, the reaction of $[\text{Pt}(\text{dien})\text{Cl}]^+$ with glutathione produces the stable binuclear $[\{\text{Pt}(\text{dien})\}_2(\mu\text{-S-glutH}_3)]^{3+}$ complex⁶⁶. The reaction is second order, involving a direct nucleophilic attack of the tripeptide sulfur atom on platinum⁶⁷. The reaction of *trans*- $[\text{PtCl}_2(\text{NH}_3)_2]$ with glutathione in aqueous solution follows a pathway involving S-coordinated glutathione⁶⁸. A recent report on the kinetics of dimethyl sulphoxide entry into the coordination sphere of $[\text{Pt}(8\text{-aminoquinoline})\text{Cl}_2]$ measured through spectrophotometry⁶⁹, shows the replacement of one Cl^- from the complex. ^1H NMR signals for the aromatic protons in the complex change with time, suggesting the Pt-S bond formation. Owing to this, the pi-electron cloud of sulfur-oxygen multiple bond in DMSO approaches closely to the 8-aminoquinoline moiety. Hence the aromatic protons interact with the pi-electron cloud of sulfur-oxygen bond causing significant changes in ^1H NMR signals.

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Ray *et al.* : Reactions of some platinum(II) complexes – hydrolysis, ring opening and substitution

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